

The Simmering Territorial Dispute In South China Sea: A Legal Perspective

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Abstract

Since the ancient times and for centuries, South China Sea has been the hub of transmission of trade, culture and political power in its neighboring countries from the main centers of power located in China and India. It has been the medium of communication and transportations for trade goods through merchant fleets, ships and vessels. Besides that, it has been the center of naval fleets moving to Indian oceans and Pacific oceans for political access in South East Asia. South China Sea has always been noteworthy to China, for being an area of influence due to its location. Currently, it is evolving as an important pillar of China's national interest and national sovereignty which is based on the substantial features of the South China Sea. However, along with China, there are other countries such as Philippine and Vietnam with their strong claims either on the basis of historical influence or on the basis of United Nations' Convention on the Law of Sea.

Introduction

South China Sea is located in the South East of Asia surrounded by Vietnam and Borneo from the West, Philippines and Indonesia from East and South, and by China from North and North West, Indonesia and North by China. China's maritime claims on a vast part of the sea and developments of artificial islands are certainly creating a conflicting situation within the region since the South China Sea is not claimed by China only, rather by five other countries of Southeast Asia which includes Malaysia, Philippine, Vietnam, Brunei and Singapore and Taiwan. Claims made by Singapore, Brunei and Malaysia are minor in nature while the claims by Taiwan are equally important to that of Peoples' Republic of China. Both have commonality in nature of claims as both endorse each other's claim. According to the Republic of China (ROC, Taiwan) in terms of either historical, geographical or international legal perspective, the Nansha (Spratly) Islands, Shisha (Paracel) Islands, Chungsha (Macclesfield) Islands, Tungsha (Paratas) Islands, as well as their surrounding waters, their respective Seabed and subsoil belong to the Republic of China' as 'an inherent part of the territory'. The ROC 'does not recognize any claim to sovereignty over, or occupation of, these areas by other countries' (Position Paper on ROC South China Sea Policy, 2016). However, Philippine and Vietnam are the major claimant of the Sea and particularly the area which is claimed by China in South and South East of China. China claims a largest portion of the sea in the form of 'nine dash line', with nine dotted lines stretched from South of Hainan island province of China towards Indonesia, Malaysia, Brunei and Philippine. The dotted 'nine dash line' and subsequent developments are attracting the concerns of other regional and global powers including Japan, India and the US. Dispute the South China Sea has been warned by many analysts including the Robert Kaplan, a geo-strategist that it is "the 21st century's defining battleground" the "throat of global Sea routes" (Kaplan R. D., 2011). Because of its relevance for the states located around the sea and for operational military implications. The South China Sea has become a source of conflict among East Asian countries due to the above-mentioned factors. Different countries claim different islands of the Sea, but the main conflict is over the Islands of Spratly and Paracel (Cronin, 2013). There is a matter of concern for the eastern and western scholars who question the reason why China is passionate for possessing the largest portion of the sea as well as the reason why it has been developed as a core in China's foreign policy.

Along with an analysis of the current situation, development and nature of claims on historical basis, there is a need to identify the case from a legal perspective. Since the conflicting hurdles sprouting from land possession claims and political ownership do not fulfil the legal criterion. In this regard, the United Nations' Convention on Law of Sea is significant in providing the legal basis of simmering maritime disputes. The UNCLOS have ordained few principles to testify the truth of claims and the consequent resolution of the issue.

Following questions would be the core of the research:

1. What is the status of South China sea and how China is making developments along South China Sea?
2. Why China is so concerned for South China Sea Security dynamics?
3. What is the status of South China Sea in context of UNCLOS?

The current research is a significant contribution to existing body of knowledge since it not only highlights the nature of dispute, sort of China's claims, position of other claimants along with the nature of claims in legal perspectives. Besides this, ongoing study investigates the significance of the Sea in context of law. The study has been divided into three segments, its opening segment explores the brief introduction including its scope, correlation of China 'claims, claims of other South East Asian states and UNCLOS rise along with significant queries. It also deals with the methods and technologies employed to analyze the collected data. Second segment analyzes the UNCLOS and its efficacy that how the maritime claims are interlinked with claims made by China. The Last segment articulates the relationship of ongoing simmering dispute in context of Law on Sea.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tønnesson investigates South China Sea which has got fascination since 2009 when different clashes over drilling, fishing, naval exercises, started to occur in regions involving China, Philippine, Vietnam. Moreover, he claims that although China is rising and adopting aggressive stances occasionally, but after all, it will go with negotiations over the conflict under international law, which otherwise could hinder it to take further moves to develop. Further he introduces the interesting geopolitical notion that maritime territorial disputes are intrinsically less likely to lead to war than disputes over land borders (Tønnesson, 2015). However, he ignores the other economic and political factors that are tremendous hindrances in dealing with this issue.

Yann-huei Song and Keyuan Sou in their edited work collect all the well-known names on the maritime aggression and the resulting global concerns to take their views on the different dimensions of the Sea and particularly about its legal position on different chains of islands of Paracels and Sparty (Sou, July 2015). Further suggestions for the regional code of conduct and methods to resolve the conflict have been discussed by security specialists, lawyers, military officers and people from academics and research from America, Europe and Taiwan.

S Jayakumar with his fellows analyse the different provisions of the UNCLOS and their feasibility to apply on South China Sea with extensive details. Further major details including history development and current status of legal principles are also discussed. Moreover, legal principles are discussed with the domestic as well as global implications. This book is an informative account on the maritime law with the application of law on South China Sea from a neutral point of view which can be valuable for the future in addressing the clash, access to resources and upcoming challenges to the navigational freedom (S Jayakumar, 2014). The UNCLOS is a legal framework which presents the legal principles for the viable advances within the oceans and resources. Nong Hong explains the effectiveness and application of UNCLOS and evaluates it as a main source of settlement of maritime disputes. South China Sea has been taken as the most challenging case study to apply the 'internal coherence of the law' on the maritime issues and the measures to settle them (Hong, 2012). Shicun Wu along with Mark Valencia talk about the security and political dimensions of South China Sea with all the technical themes like marine scientific research, historic claims, navigation regimes, regional common heritage, use of oceans (Shicun Wu, 2016). In this edited book, different writers from diverse backgrounds have given their views on different dimensions of the Sea related issues generally while regarding South China Sea in particular. This book is important because of its subject matter related to ASEAN countries and particularly the tensions arising from the South China Sea dispute. As South China Sea is a significant and current issues, most of the literature covering all dimensions is in edited version which is a result of the conference on the dimensions of the Sea. In this regard, Robert C. Beckman, with other co-authors have edited a book based on the deposits of resources and then emphasized over the improvement of the nature of the issue and the efforts to settle the issue (Robert C. Beckman et al, 2013). Along with UNCLOS, the major details including history development and current status of legal principles are also discussed with domestic as well as global implications. This book is an informative account on the maritime law with the application of law on South China Sea with neutral point of view which can be valuable for the future in addressing the clash, access to resources and upcoming challenges to the freedom of navigation. According to Leszek Buszynski, South China Sea is a dispute which has existed since the last six decades and is becoming more complex day by day as states have become more assertive and aggressive in nature to their claims on different parts of the Sea. As a gateway to major supply lines particularly for power engine like Korea and Japan, China in this regard is absolute in its claims that it has indisputable sovereignty which is drawing in the US which is more concerned about the regional stability and the insurance of freedom of navigation. In this regard, the US is evolving ties with Vietnam besides the Philippine whom it has been supporting for years, however, currently it is developing different security ties to keep an eye on China. It has examined the extent of potential lies within the conflict and diagnoses the peaceful resolution to avoid any future threat to regional as well as global security (Buszynski, 2014). Discussions have been made in multiple directions. The current developments made in South China Sea have been analysed by comprehending the international view point in the legal perspectives with the involvement of different actors in conflict at regional and international levels. Meanwhile, application of international law in changing regional context and particularly in the changing political landscape along different previous policies are discussed to manage the conflict peacefully. At the same time, current policy

implications as well as the future policy options are also discussed. Urge has been made on peaceful resolution of dispute by giving diverse view points on the subject (Tran Truong Thuy, 2015). Shicun Wu with Keyuan Zou discusses the decision of International Court of Arbitration which was filed against China by Philippines under the (United Nations Conventions on the Law of Sea) UNCLOS. The case is considered as a milestone in many perspectives but mainly because of its involvement of parties, absence of parties and legal questions to be addressed while proceedings. As an edited version, the book is a collection of all facts and figures shared in proceedings by different scholars from North America, Europe and Asia raised out of the South China Sea Arbitration. It consists of five parts, the first deals with ‘the origin and development of the South China Sea conflict’, the second deals with ‘the jurisdiction and admissibility of the case’, the third is about ‘the international adjudication and dispute settlement’, and fourth deals with the ‘legal issues arising from the case’ such as ‘the legal status of the U-shaped line and islands, rocks and low-tide elevations’ while on the other hand, the fifth deals with ‘the Arbitration case and its impact on regional maritime security (Zou, 2016).

After having a critical review of the above defined literature and other primary and secondary sources, it is concluded that there is requisite to be more focused, in analysis of the growing power of China, particularly, it is essential to have a neutral look and more of a pragmatic approach respectively. There is certainly a need to identify and understand the fine lines of growth of Chinese economy and moderation of security parameters. Although, both soft and hard powers go hand in hand, however, still it is required to find out and understand the current nature and priorities of China’s overall growth. Additionally, there must be a pragmatic, accommodative and a neutral approach in studying the policies of the US, its concerns and initiative of ‘Pivot to Asia’. Although the US was growing its ties with Asia Pacific during Obama’s regime, however, the US’s new government is also making its focus on the Asia Pacific for many reasons where South China dispute is one of those.

The current study is descriptive, analytical and explanatory in nature where available data has been analyzed, evaluated critically. In the existing research, qualitative research method is applied for collecting and analyzing the primary as well secondary data. Multiple primary and secondary sources have been consulted in order to get the actual underpinnings. Primary data is consisted on white papers of China and other unclassified official documents. While secondary data is consisted on articles, academic reports published by academic institutions, news agencies and government institutions.

Maritime Issues in Legal Framework

According to the legal perspective, the sovereignty of a state on an island can be identified if the occupation and administration are continuous for a long period of time and a peaceful one. This principle of maritime sovereignty was put forward in ‘Palmas Case’, in April 4, 1928 by Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) which gave decision on a case, based on islands initially discovered by Spain, however, later was occupied by Netherlands. The US claimed its sovereignty on the basis of its discovery as Spain’s successor in Philippines which was rejected by the arbitrator Max Huber. The claim on the basis of right of discovery was considered incomplete without the right of peaceful and consistent state sovereignty on those islands. Thus, Max Huber decided the case in the favour of Netherland for its peaceful and continuous occupation of the islands (reports of international arbitral awards *recueil des sentences arbitrales islands of palm case 1928*, 2006).

The same principle of continuous peaceful occupation and state authority were used in decision of El Salvador/Honduras by the International Court of Justice in 1992 (Shaw, 1993). In the scenario of Eretria/Yemen case in 1998, a similar principle was adopted to decide the dispute. In 2002, the same principle of occupation and administration was followed by the International Court of Justice (ICJ) in the decision of dispute between Malaysia and Indonesia. In this case, many steps taken by Malaysia in favour of Oceanic life were taken as administrative steps, thus the case was decided in Malaysia’s favour (reports of international arbitral awards *recueil des sentences arbitrales islands of palm case 1928*, 2006).

Beside the principles of peaceful and continuous occupation, another important principle was ordained by the United Nations (UN) Convention in 1982 that was about the 200 nautical mile (nm) Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) as is mentioned in the Article 76 (part VI) (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, 1994). In addition to it, the United Nations Convention on Law of Sea (UNCLOS) does not support the claims which go beyond EEZs or declared Continental Shelves mentioned in International Law. The area which is claimed by China is beyond the EEZ of China and goes towards the EEZ of other claimant states of South East Asia. (Buszynski, *The South China Sea: Oil, Maritime Claims, and U.S.—China Strategic Rivalry*, 2012). Although the International Law accepts the historical rights but not the “historic bays” which are mentioned in Article 10(6) (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, 1994). According to the UNCLOS, the historical basis of claims has to meet these three criteria: 1) demonstrated authority, 2) continuity of exercising the authority, 3) recognition of authority by the other states.

The UNCLOS demonstrated the demands made by the developing countries which proposed for 10 nm from baseline that was later extended from 10 nm to 80 nm, during informal consultations made in the Law of the Sea Conference. Up to now, it has been extended to 125 nm from baselines. The original draft did not allow the use of low tide elevations for lighthouse purposes to show the enclosing points of an archipelago while according to

Article 118 in the Law of the Sea Conferences of informal negotiations, it is allowed. (Diplomatic conferences, 1958). The Law of the Sea Conference provided the passage in the form of port facility to the foreign ships in section 3, which included the right to stop and anchoring the overseas ships. Innocent passage is innocent as long as it does not create any threat to security of the host state maritime. Further, in order to maintain the security, innocent passages provide the right to the host maritime states to halt the maritime traffic of foreign ships. However, Straits are exempted from it to ensure the freedom of navigation. For the same reasons, it would be considered illegal to halt the navigation in Malacca Strait while in case of Spratly Islands it will be legal (Diplomatic conferences, 1958).

China and the Law of the Sea

The UNCLOS with its particular on straits and 200 nm EEZ were extensively accepted by the developing states except the few states like Brazil, Peru and Ecuador who supported China in opposing it. During China's period, it did not stretch its territorial sea to 200 nm. Earlier to that, China wrote a letter to the Delegation of the Japan-China Fishery Council in 1963 which announced that beyond the 12 twelve-mile territorial limit, China had two security zones where China had authority to halt and ban the foreign ships or where a permission would be required or advised to avoid. According to those economic zones, one would be prohibited for all type of navigation while other zone would be prohibited, without prior consent of the Chinese government (Chiu, 1963).

Besides the above-mentioned zones, another zone has also been established which is known as the South Zone of 27 degree in East of Mainland to halt the Japanese fishing boats in the military operations area. Few other things were also made clear that a state is sovereign over its waters so the right to allow or prohibit someone to give the innocent passage depends on the state. Same is the case with straits in dealing with foreign ships. A similar stance was adopted by insisting on states to determine their own sea boundary during the Third Law of the Sea Conference in 1973.

If China adopts the position to have 200 miles as a territorial sea, it would create a conflicting situation among the neighboring maritime countries around the South East Asia and East Asia. It led to the debate on whether China should adopt 200 miles for territorial Sea or for the exclusive economic zone (EEZ) (Katchen, 1977).

Although the notion of state sovereignty dates back to the Treaty of Westphalia in the 17th and 18th century while the notion of maritime sovereignty is a very recent one which developed during 1945. During that time, the US demanded sovereignty for control on its territorial waters. In order to deal with the issue of sovereignty, the UN law on Sea agreements described the conditions for maritime sovereignty which were similar however the claims founded on historical basis were rejected. In this regard, there is a significant point to note that China claims almost 80 % of the Sea as its 'historic' waters.

It has been a tradition since the ancient times that powerful states control, annex and assimilate other territories through aggression or physical force. Thus, the expansion and contraction of the states and empires has been a custom. Same occurred in the case of China, during the Qin, Han, Tang, Song, and Ming dynasties, China saw its rise and fall and practiced its expansionist policies in Inner Asia and Indochina region. The gradual expansion of China which took place during the non-Chinese Manchu and Mongols towards Xingjian, Tibet, Taiwan and Southeast Asia were the empire states practicing the rhetoric of modern nation-state (Malik, 2013). Turning back to history on the nature of modern state formation as well as the historical claims of China, then it can be analyzed that other main claimant states also have their own claims on a similar historical basis. On the basis of historical evidence, the Malay people who belong to the currently known Philippine may also claim for Taiwan more strongly than China as Taiwan was settled by the people of Malay-Polynesian origin. Also, the claims in South China Sea are similar to the Mexican claims in the Gulf of Mexico, Iran's on the Persian Gulf, and India on the Indian Ocean (Malik, 2013).

UNCLOS: Specific Articles and their Application on South China Sea

Fig 1

Source: (MIRASOLA, 2015)

According to United Nation Convention on the Law of Sea (UNCLOS), there are different specifications for countries on their maritime jurisdictions based on different fulfilling criteria. In case of the coastal states, three aspects are very significant regarding the physical features in UNCLOS, in outlining the maritime claims:

Islands: "A landmass permanently above water that can sustain human habitation or economic life on its own. It is entitled to a territorial sea, contiguous zone, EEZ or continental shelf Rights". According to the UNCLOS part VIII, Article 121, 'an Island is a naturally formed area of land, surrounded by water, which is above water at high tide'. 'The territorial sea, the contiguous zone, the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf of an island are determined in accordance with the provisions of this Convention applicable to other land territory' (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, 1994).

Reefs: "A landmass permanently above water but unable to sustain human habitation or economic life on its own. It is entitled to a territorial sea and contiguous zone, but not an exclusive economic zone (EEZ) or continental shelf rights". According to the UNCLOS, the rocks which cannot sustain human habitation or economic life of their own shall have no exclusive economic zone or continental shelf.

Low tide: "A landmass above water only at low tide. Outside an existing territorial sea it is not entitled to a separate maritime zone" (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, 1994). For further clarification here are the specific articles of UNCLOS which deal with these maritime issues.

Article 121: Regime of islands

1. "An island is a naturally formed area of land, surrounded by water, which is above water at high tide".
2. "Except as provided for in paragraph 3, the territorial sea, the contiguous zone, the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf of an island are determined in accordance with the provisions of this Convention applicable to other land territory".
3. "Rocks which cannot sustain human habitation or economic life of their own shall have no exclusive economic zone or continental shelf".

Article 3: Breadth of the territorial sea, "Every State has the right to establish the breadth of its territorial sea up to a limit not exceeding 12 nautical miles, measured from baselines determined in accordance with this Convention".

Article 6: Reefs, "In the case of islands situated on atolls or of islands having fringing reefs, the baseline for measuring the breadth of the territorial sea is the seaward low-water line of the reef, as shown by the appropriate symbol on charts officially recognized by the coastal State".

Article 13: Low-tide elevations,

1. "A low-tide elevation is a naturally formed area of land which is surrounded by and above water at low tide but submerged at high tide. Where a low-tide elevation is situated wholly or partly at a distance not exceeding the breadth of the territorial sea from the mainland or an island, the low-water line on that elevation may be used as the baseline for measuring the breadth of the territorial sea".
2. "Where a low-tide elevation is wholly situated at a distance exceeding the breadth of the territorial sea from the mainland or an island, it has no territorial sea of its own".

Article 33: Contiguous zone,

1. "In a zone contiguous to its territorial sea, described as the contiguous zone, the coastal State may exercise the control necessary to:
 - a. "Prevent infringement of its customs, fiscal, immigration or sanitary laws and regulations within its territory or territorial sea;
 - b. Punish infringement of the above laws and regulations committed within its territory or territorial sea".

2. “The contiguous zone may not extend beyond 24 nautical miles from the baselines from which the breadth of the territorial sea is measured”.

Article 76 Definition of the Continental Shelf

“The continental shelf of a coastal State comprises the seabed and subsoil of the submarine areas that extend beyond its territorial sea throughout the natural prolongation of its land territory to the outer edge of the continental margin, or to a distance of 200 nautical miles from the baselines from which the breadth of the territorial sea is measured where the outer edge of the continental margin does not extend up to that distance”.

Article 55: Specific legal regime of the exclusive economic zone

“The exclusive economic zone is an area beyond and adjacent to the territorial sea, subject to the specific legal regime established in this Part, under which the rights and jurisdiction of the coastal State and the rights and freedoms of other States are governed by the relevant provisions of this Convention”.

Article 56: Rights, jurisdiction and duties of the coastal State in the exclusive economic zone

In the exclusive economic zone, the coastal State has:

- (a) “sovereign rights for the purpose of exploring and exploiting, conserving and managing the natural resources, whether living or non-living, of the waters superjacent to the seabed and of the seabed and its subsoil, and with regard to other activities for the economic exploitation and exploration of the zone, such as the production of energy from the water, currents and winds;
- (b) Jurisdiction as provided for in the relevant provisions of this Convention with regard to:
- The establishment and use of artificial islands, installations and structures;
 - Marine scientific research;
 - The protection and preservation of the marine environment;
- (c) Other rights and duties provided for in this Convention.

In exercising its rights and performing its duties under this Convention in the exclusive economic zone EEZ, the coastal State shall have due regard to the rights and duties of other States and shall act in a manner compatible with the provisions of this Convention. The rights set out in this article with respect to the seabed and subsoil shall be exercised in accordance with Part VI” (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, 1994).

Since 1970s, China has controlled the northern part of these islands by expelling Vietnamese forces from the area while during 1980s and 1990s, China controlled the seven reefs out of 200 while in 2012, and it took the control of Scarborough Shoal.

Status of various islands and reefs

Sn	Name of feature	Country	Status
1	Johnson South Reef	China	Rock, installed radar and guns
2.	Subi Reef	China	LTE, runway and telecom facilities
3	Mischief Reef	China	LTE Runway and telecom facilities
4	Fiery Cross Reef	China	Rock, built 3,000m runway and port
5	Cuateron Reef	China	Rock, built operates lighthouse
6	Gaven Reef	China	LTE, built heliport
7	Hughes Reef	China	LTE, installed radar and other facilities
8	Thitu Island	Philippines	Inhabited by civilian and military personnel
9	Spratly Island	Vietnam	Upgraded electricity supply
10	Itu Aba Island	Taiwan	Dock for large warships
11	Swallow Reef	Malaysia	Runway and resort

Source: *Nikkei Asian Review*

Table 1

Source: (Manoj, 2016)

The sovereignty over waters is a complex matter which in this regard, two aspects are important to highlight: the first one is based on the features through which sovereignty can be established, while the second is based on the features which give a state the status of a coastal state. In determining the sovereignty of a coastal state (PART V Exclusive Economic Zone), the breadth of the territorial sea in the low water line along the coast is considered as a normal baseline. Low tide lines are also known as the dry rocks or dry shoals, which cannot be considered as islands. Islands are considered the high tide elevation, which are the ‘naturally formed area of land’. Within the jurisdiction of Exclusive economic Zones and territorial waters artificial islands can be made for security reasons however they would not be taken as the islands (PART V Exclusive Economic Zone). Within internal waters, a coastal state has jurisdiction to carry out any activity of installation, construction, or

any other infrastructure without interruption while if a foreign state aims to install some pipeline or cable, it is necessary to attain permission from the coastal /host state. While the host state is granted exclusive jurisdiction in the Exclusive Economic Zones along with the safety of artificial islands and installations within EEZ, however, these safety zones cannot exceed the limit of 500 meters.

According to UNCLOS, states could have 12 nautical miles out to sea as territorial zone, and a further 12 nautical miles as a contiguous zone. Thus states could have a total area of 200 nautical miles as Exclusive Economic Zone. States can extend their jurisdiction to 350 nautical miles in case of the continental shelf. In case of islands, coastal states would have a territorial sea and Exclusive Economic Zone while in case of rocks, no Exclusive Economic Zone would be allowed but only the territorial sea (PART V Exclusive Economic Zone).

Map: 2

Upon UNCLOS, China has the argument that at the time of ratification, the UNCLOS in June 1996 has already defined its maritime boundaries after consultations with the neighbouring states and reaffirmed 'its sovereignty over all its archipelagos and islands' under Article 2 on February 1992 Law on Territorial Sea and Contiguous Zones. All disputed islands within Japan, Taiwan, Vietnam and Philippine were included. Plenty of negotiations and discussions led China to deal with the Gulf of Tonkin between China and Vietnam. The current tension surged in 2009 when the UN Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS), given deadline to the states to submit their claims for continental shelf beyond the 200 nautical miles of Exclusive Economic zone which led many bold claims by various states on uninhabited maritime features and a step forward to the solidification of the claims (PART V Exclusive Economic Zone). In this regard, in 2009 a joint Malaysian-Vietnamese reference in accordance with Article 76, paragraph 8, of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea was made to the UN Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS) that there are few unresolved disputes in the southern part of South China Sea with a detailed map. At the same time, a note verbale by the Permanent Mission of China in UN announced with a map based on Nine Dashes that 'China has indisputable sovereignty over the islands in South China Sea and the adjacent waters and this joint submission has infringed the Chinese sovereignty, sovereign rights and the jurisdiction in South China Sea'. In accordance with Article 5 (a) of the Annex I to the Rules of Procedure of Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS), the Chinese government made a request 'to not consider the joint reference made by Malaysia and Vietnam'.

Vietnam responded by its own note verbale addressed to the Secretary General of UN on 8 May 2009 over the Hong Sa (Paracel) and Truong Sa (Spratlys) that Vietnamese submission is under the legitimate parameters of UNCLOS 1982 and the Rules of Procedure of Commission of on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS), while Chinese claims and maps attached have no legal, historical or factual basis (The permanent Mission of Peoples Republic of Chona to UN, 2009). Malaysia's claims on the continental shelf originated from UNCLOS so it is out of scrutiny. Philippines in this regard took a unique position and claimed that the Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS had to ignore the Malaysia-Vietnam joint submission as they were overlapping with the Philippines claims. Also, it mentioned another dispute of Sabah with Malaysia. It became very clear after the exchange of notes by other claimant states that many had their rising conflicts based on China's claims. Later in 2009, Indonesia issued a note verbale which stated that although Indonesia was not a claimant state on the disputant areas of South China Sea, however it had reservations of dotted lines known as 'nine dash' line that they had no legal basis and explanation for drawing those lines. The Indonesian note said in reference to China's note that 'it is only correct to state that those remote of very small features in the South China Sea do not deserve exclusive zone or continental shelf of their own', to make baseline to the 'uninhabited rocks, reefs and atolls' would be a matter of great concern

for the UNCLOS and the international community. Meanwhile in 2009, another note was submitted by China in addition to the previous note of 7 May 2009 that “China’s sovereignty and related rights and jurisdiction in South China Sea are supported by abundant historical and legal evidence.” It emphasized that Philippine never claimed these areas prior to 1970 on Nansha (Spratlys) while China had outlined the ‘geographical scope’ of Nansha (Spratlys) with ‘territorial sea, exclusive economic zone (EEZ) and continental shelf’ since 1930s.

Although China has made the claims on many bases, however, there are two confusions about those claims: one is based on the fact that China’s claims over the entire areas existed within the ‘nine dash line’, while other is based on lack of clarity of the claims; if China’s claims are valid, then on what possible Articles they are accelerated as per the norms of UNCLOS. The confusion is that either China is making claims within ‘nine dash line’ as a national boundary or it only wants to claim on seabed and seabed resources. No matter what intention of China is, it declares the under discussion islands chain as indisputable part of their territory.

From the above discussion of UNCLOS and its provisions, it is evident that China is making claims on political basis which have been supported by historical accounts consisting of travellers and ambassadors accounts. Political claims are also confusing as these are overlapping with Vietnam, Philippines, Malaysia, Indonesia, Brunei and Taiwan. The political claim drawn on 1947 was officially converted by 2009 note verbale which was immediately responded by the neighbours as mentioned by the Freedom of Navigation, Department of Defence US (DoD Releases 2015 Fiscal Year Freedom of Navigation Report, 2016). In case of China, the status of South China Sea as a ‘historic waters’ has no justification in the International Law since China took the eastern part of Paracel islands in May 1950. In 1974, Chinese vessels clashed with Vietnam vessels and ousted them from the western part of Paracel Islands with the subsequent control of the entire Paracel islands. However, in the case of Spratly, China did not make any occupation in 1988, until it took the control from Vietnam after a naval clash when it had planted the flag on seven rocks and atolls. Meanwhile, China could have the benefit of occupation over the island. To strengthen its case, China justified its occupation since the ancient times. Nevertheless, Max Huber in ‘Palmas case’ tested it clearly that the occupations based on an archaic time period would not be accepted if it was not in accordance to the modern International law. In other words, it had to meet the requirement of occupation of the modern law as well (Buszynski, *The South China Sea Maritime Dispute: Political, Legal and Regional Perspectives*, 2014).

CONCLUSION

Consequently, according to the legal perspective, China cannot claim for the jurisdiction of islands on the basis of peaceful and continuous occupation with a complete authority of state. On the same basis, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) gave its ruling case in favour of Philippine against China in 2016. At the same time, China had its own justification for South China Sea as an ‘indisputable territory’ on the basis of its own evidences mainly presented by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

Through a detailed analysis of the claims made by the three major competitors, it is evident that almost all states’ claims are based on historical basis. These claims have developed with the passage of time and have been the ‘national interests’ of each state. Thus, a critical dispute which has a potential to be a major future conflict should be dealt with a sense of responsibility. A peaceful solution based on mutual consensus of parties involved in the dispute is highly required.

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